

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D3.1 PreMETS certification framework

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Microcredential certification framework

Microcredential certification current status and best practices

Microcredentials in the EU are defined as digital records of learning outcomes acquired from short, targeted educational experiences. These outcomes are assessed against transparent, clearly defined criteria and verified by trusted bodies (Bozkurt & Brown, 2022). The core principles include:

- **Assessment:** Outcomes are assessed against established standards.
- **Quality Assurance:** Processes are quality-assured and verified by reputable organizations.
- **Transparency:** Certificates provide detailed metadata, including learner identity, awarding body, date of issue, study hours, credit value, and level.

The European Commission has developed guidelines to ensure consistency and quality in microcredential offerings across member states. These guidelines emphasize the importance of stackability, allowing microcredentials to be combined with other qualifications or used independently as proof of specific skills and knowledge (Bozkurt & Brown, 2022). Several of these guidelines are stated in the European Digital Credentials for Learning framework¹, which will be described below. There is also a large selection of micro-credential providers. Often, the credentials are provided in collaboration across various types of organisations, such as higher education institutions, businesses and non-governmental organisations.

Higher education institutions play an active role in this field. They provide credit-bearing micro-credentials (for which a learner earns credits at the completion) and non-credit-bearing micro-credentials (for which a learner does not earn credits). They organise their alternative credential programmes usually through the departments of continuing education or in partnership with other higher education institutions (e.g., European Consortium of Innovative Universities,² Young Universities for the Future of Europe³) or with online programme managers such as 2U,⁴ Online Education Services⁵ and Keypath. These offer online course development for micro-credentials, degree courses, and MOOCs, either on a global

¹ <https://europass.europa.eu/en/europass-tools/european-digital-credentials>

² <https://www.eciu.org/>

³ <https://www.yufe.eu/>

⁴ <https://2u.com/>

⁵ <https://www.oes.edu.au>

platform (e.g., Coursera, edX, FutureLearn, Udacity, XuetangX etc.) or on the institution's own platform.⁶

In Europe, the European MOOC Consortium, including FutureLearn, France Université Numérique (FUN), OpenupED, Miríadax, EduOpen and coordinated by EADTU, has published the Common Microcredential Framework (CMF). The aim of the framework is to standardise the range of micro-credentials offered by the leading European MOOC platforms and the universities in their networks and to support institutions in creating a new type of international and transferable credential for lifelong learning. This framework sets out the following criteria for all new micro-credentials:

- Have a total workload of no less than 100 hours and no more than 150 hours (4-6 ECTS⁷), including revision for, and completion of, the summative assessment.
- Be classified at level 6 (Bachelor), level 7 (Master) and level 8 (Doctoral) with option for level 5 (in combination with ECTS) of the European Qualification Framework or the equivalent levels in the university's national qualification framework.
- Provide an assessment that enables the award of academic credit, either on successful completion of the course or through recognition of prior learning on enrolment as a student on the university's course of study.
- Adopt a reliable process of verifying ID at the time of assessment that complies with the university's policies and/or is widely adopted across the platforms authorised to use the CMF.
- Provide a transcript that sets out the learning outcomes for a course, total study hours required, EQF level and number of credit points earned.

European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS)

ECTS is an instrument that expresses the volume of learning based on defined learning outcomes and the associated workload. ECTS credits are applicable to programmes regardless of mode of delivery, status of students (full-time, part-time) and learning context (formal, non-formal and informal)⁸.

ECTS credits are allocated to various educational components such as course units, work-based learning and work placements. The starting point for credit allocation is that the achievement of the intended learning outcomes equivalent to the

⁶ <https://microbol.knowledgeinnovation.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2020/09/MICROBOL-Desk-Research-Report.pdf>

⁷ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/inclusive-and-connected-higher-education/european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system>

⁸ <https://microbol.knowledgeinnovation.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/20/2020/09/MICROBOL-Desk-Research-Report.pdf>

workload of a full-time academic year equals 60 ECTS credits. Generally, the workload ranges from 1,500 to 1,800 hours for an academic year. This means that the typical workload of 25 to 30 hours corresponds to one ECTS credit with actual time for achievement of learning outcomes varying from one student to another. ECTS facilitates the transfer of credits and thus, facilitates learners' mobility. There are several documents that facilitate the use of ECTS, namely the Course Catalogue, Learning Agreement, Transcript of Records, and the Work Placement Certificate. ECTS credits may be awarded through assessment or recognition of the learning outcomes achieved, including those achieved in non-formal or informal learning contexts, and a learner can accumulate credits either to obtain qualifications or to document personal achievements. The 2015 ECTS Users' Guide specifies that ECTS credits can be used in lifelong learning contexts (including continuing and professional education) applying the same principles for credit allocation, award, accumulation and transfer. Regarding the allocation of ECTS credits to qualifications or programmes, the 2015 ECTS Users' Guide specifies that it should be done in accordance with national legislation and practice. In cases where providers that are not formally recognized educational institutions are not allowed to award ECTS credits due to legal restrictions, it may still be advisable for them to refer indirectly to ECTS credits, provided that such references comply with the legal and regulatory framework. This can help learners to understand the workload and level of the course in a familiar context. However, it is important to clearly state that the credits are not officially awarded under the ECTS system and that the provider is not authorized to issue formal ECTS credits.

European Digital Credentials for Learning framework

A credential, in its most essential form, is a documented statement containing claims made about a person.

- European Digital Credentials for Learning (Figure 1) are standardised tamper-evident electronic documents describing that their owner has certain skills or has achieved certain learning outcomes through formal or non-formal learning context.
- A digitally-signature (e-Seal) guarantees the origin and integrity of the document.
- The European Learning Model allows interoperability of Learning Opportunities, Qualifications and Credentials in Europe and supports a fast track to credential recognition, reducing administrative burden and decreasing fraud (Figure 2) by supporting automatic authentication of qualifications by employers and training providers.⁹

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http://sepie.es/doc/comunicacion/jornadas/2021/21_diciembre/europass/1_edc_sepie_infoday2021.pdf

System Functions

Figure 1: European Digital Credentials for Learning - System Functions

Source:

http://sepie.es/doc/comunicacion/jornadas/2021/21_diciembre/europass/1_edc_sepie_infoday2021.pdf

Online Verification method could be linked directly to the Europass wallet (EDC Issue system) or via a third-party authorization platform for educational programs (i.e., Digitary, Credly, or Accredible) and it will be stored/accessed by the student via the Europass wallet (Europass verified).

Figure 2: European Digital Credentials for Learning - Automated Certificate Issue and Verification framework

Source:

http://sepie.es/doc/comunicacion/jornadas/2021/21_diciembre/europass/1_edc_sepie_infoday2021.pdf

Digital Seal

An organization that may officially issue and offer certificates with a Digital Seal (eSeal) must be an authorized entity/organization capable of offering vocational training seminars, courses and other educational activities. For this reason, the organization needs an active VAT number. Therefore, the PreMETS consortium needs an eSeal, which is not possible as there is no VAT identification number. For this reason, PreMETS consortium decided to provide through their platform a digitally signed credential linked to the PreMETS identity, such that only the PreMETS entity may issue such a credential.

Several options of eSeal are:

- eSeal (advanced): Advanced electronic seal for documents (e.g. pdf) including information of the associated organization
- eSeal (qualified): Qualified electronic seal for documents (e.g. pdf) including information of the associated organization
- eSeal - PSD2 (advanced) : Advanced electronic seal for documents (e.g. pdf) including information of the associated organization and its identification is designated by the National Competent Authorities (NCAs) according to Payment Service Directive 2 (EU) 2015/2366
- eSeal - PSD2 (qualified) : Qualified electronic seal for documents (e.g. pdf) including information of the associated organization and its identification is designated by the National Competent Authorities (NCAs) according to Payment Service Directive 2 (EU) 2015/2366¹⁰.

Learning Management Systems (LMS)

Creating a platform to host Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) for predictive maintenance requires a robust Learning Management System (LMS) that supports diverse learning formats, offers scalability, and integrates well with various tools. Here are several LMS options suitable for such a deployment:

1. Moodle

Moodle is an open-source LMS known for its adaptability and customizability. It supports a wide range of instructional activities, including quizzes, assignments, and forums, which are crucial for MOOCs. Moodle's active user community continually contributes to its development, making it a reliable choice for hosting large-scale online courses.

Moodle, as a widely-used Learning Management System (LMS), has the capacity to support microcredential certification systems in line with the European Digital Credentials for Learning standards. Here's an overview of how Moodle aligns with these standards and the processes involved and its capacity for Microcredentials:

¹⁰ <https://www.harica.gr/en/Products/eSeal>

- **Metadata Management:** Moodle can include detailed metadata for microcredentials, such as the learner's identity, the issuing institution, the date of issue, and the learning outcomes achieved. This capability is essential for meeting the European standards.
- **Verification and Quality Assurance:** Moodle supports the issuance of digital badges and certificates that can be verified by trusted bodies, ensuring the authenticity and quality of the credentials.
- **Integration with European Digital Infrastructures:** Moodle can interact with platforms like Europass, allowing institutions to issue credentials that comply with the European Digital Credentials Infrastructure. This includes the use of technologies like Blockchain for secure and fraud-resistant credentialing.
- **Customization and Scalability:** As an open-source platform, Moodle can be customized to meet specific institutional needs for microcredentialing. It supports the creation, management, and tracking of learning modules that can be stacked to form larger qualifications.

Moodle has been used effectively to handle practical exercises and project-based learning, ensuring that credentials issued are aligned with both national and European frameworks (Tomsič, Demsar, & Finkšt, 2020). Similarly, a project like MicroHE has developed the Credentify platform, which integrates with Moodle to display, verify, and share microcredential data using Blockchain technology (Berkling et al., 2023).

2. Canvas

Canvas, developed by Instructure, is a cloud-based LMS widely used in educational settings. It offers robust tools for course creation, student collaboration, and real-time analytics. Canvas is particularly known for its user-friendly interface and strong mobile app integration, which ensures learners can access courses on the go. While Canvas excels in providing a versatile platform for course creation, student engagement, and assessment, its specific integration with European Digital Credentials for Learning standards, particularly for microcredentials, requires careful consideration. Here's an overview of how Canvas aligns with these standards and the processes involved and its capacity for Microcredentials:

- **Course Creation and Management:** Canvas provides comprehensive tools for creating and managing courses, including multimedia integration, assessments, and interactive learning activities (Md Zin, 2023). These tools are essential for developing microcredential programs that meet high educational standards.
- **Assessment and Certification:** Canvas supports various assessment strategies, including quizzes, assignments, and peer reviews, which can be used to evaluate learning outcomes necessary for microcredentialing (Marachi & Quill, 2020).

- **Integration with External Tools:** Canvas can integrate with third-party applications, which is crucial for incorporating additional functionalities required for issuing microcredentials according to European standards (Sudaryono et al., 2021).
- **Data Security and Privacy:** Ensuring data privacy and security is a critical component of digital credentials. Canvas includes features for data protection, but there are concerns about its ability to fully protect against data harvesting or exploitation (Marachi & Quill, 2020).
- **Interoperability:** Canvas can integrate with various educational tools and platforms, potentially supporting the interoperability required for European Digital Credentials (Wicaksono et al., 2021).

Canvas has been used effectively to handle practical exercises and project-based learning by providing standardized Templates and Training: Institutions using Canvas often develop standardized course templates and offer training to faculty to ensure consistent and effective use of the platform for credentialing (Judge & Murray, 2017). Continuous evaluation and feedback from instructors and students help in refining the use of Canvas for microcredential programs. For example, customized LMS training can address specific academic disciplines' needs (Fathema & Akanda, 2020).

3. Blackboard Learn

Blackboard Learn is a mature LMS with a comprehensive set of features designed for higher education and K-12. It offers tools for video conferencing, collaborative course building, and competency-based education. Blackboard also integrates with over 200 third-party systems, enhancing its functionality. While Blackboard Learn offers robust tools for course management and online learning, integrating microcredential certification systems that align with the European Digital Credentials for Learning standards requires specific features and practices. Here's an overview of how Blackboard Learn aligns with these standards and the processes involved and its capacity for Microcredentials:

- **Course Creation and Management:** Blackboard Learn supports the creation of diverse learning activities, including assignments, quizzes, and discussion boards, which are essential for developing and assessing microcredential programs (Coopman, 2009).
- **Digital Badges and Certificates:** Blackboard allows the issuance of digital badges and certificates to recognize specific skills or learning outcomes. These digital credentials can include metadata that aligns with European standards (Rohan et al., 2017).
- **Integration with External Tools:** Blackboard can integrate with various third-party tools, enhancing its ability to support microcredentialing by incorporating additional functionalities required for compliance with European standards (Algamdi et al., 2023).

- **Data Security and Privacy:** Blackboard offers features for data protection, which are critical for ensuring the security and authenticity of digital credentials (Jirgensons & Kapenieks, 2018).

Blackboard Learn has been used effectively to handle practical exercises and project-based learning by providing Digital Badging Programs like the one developed at Eckerd College Library demonstrate how Blackboard can be used to issue digital badges for staff training, thereby supporting microcredentialing within the institution (Copenhaver & Pritchard, 2017).

4. TalentLMS

TalentLMS is a cloud-based platform tailored for small and mid-sized businesses. It provides an easy-to-use interface and rapid deployment capabilities, making it ideal for organizations needing a quick setup. It includes features such as mobile learning, gamification, and reporting tools. While TalentLMS supports various educational and training needs, its integration with microcredential certification systems according to the European Digital Credentials for Learning standards is essential to ensure that issued credentials are recognized and valued across Europe. Here's an overview of how TalentLMS aligns with these standards and the processes involved and its capacity for Microcredentials:

- **Course Creation and Management:** TalentLMS provides comprehensive tools for creating and managing courses, including quizzes, assignments, and multimedia content, which are crucial for developing and assessing microcredential programs.
- **Digital Badges and Certificates:** TalentLMS supports the issuance of digital badges and certificates, which can be used to recognize specific skills or learning outcomes. These credentials can be customized to include metadata that aligns with European standards.
- **Integration with External Tools:** TalentLMS can integrate with various third-party applications, enhancing its ability to support microcredentialing by incorporating additional functionalities required for compliance with European standards.
- **Data Security and Privacy:** TalentLMS offers features for data protection, which are critical for ensuring the security and authenticity of digital credentials.

The open-source nature of TalentLMS allows for customization to meet specific institutional needs for microcredentialing. This flexibility ensures that the platform can be tailored to align with the requirements of the European Digital Credentials for Learning standards.

5. Docebo

Docebo is an all-in-one cloud LMS that is well-suited for businesses. It offers engaging learning experiences through content authoring tools, social learning features, and robust analytics. It is known for its scalability and user-friendly design. Here's an overview of how Docebo aligns with these standards and the processes involved and its capacity for Microcredentials:

- **Course Creation and Management:** Docebo supports the creation of diverse learning activities, including courses, quizzes, and assignments, which are essential for developing and assessing microcredential programs.
- **Digital Badges and Certificates:** Docebo provides functionality for issuing digital badges and certificates to recognize specific skills or learning outcomes. These digital credentials can be customized to include metadata that aligns with European standards.
- **Integration with External Tools:** Docebo can integrate with various third-party applications, enhancing its ability to support microcredentialing by incorporating additional functionalities required for compliance with European standards.
- **Data Security and Privacy:** Docebo offers robust features for data protection, which are crucial for ensuring the security and authenticity of digital credentials.

By leveraging its robust features for course management, digital badging, and integration capabilities, institutions can effectively issue and manage microcredentials. However, achieving full compliance may require additional configurations and integrations to ensure that the credentials are transparent, verifiable, and portable.

6. Absorb LMS

Absorb LMS is a cloud-based Learning Management System designed to offer a comprehensive suite of features for online training and education. It is known for its intuitive interface and robust functionality, making it suitable for various educational and corporate training needs. Absorb LMS offers simplified course building and a user-friendly interface, making it a good choice for non-profits and SMBs. It includes features like customizable dashboards, social collaborative tools, and mobile-responsive templates.

In this context to effectively deploy these LMS for MOOCs on predictive maintenance, consider the issues presented in Figure 3 below. By selecting the right LMS and considering these implementation factors, you can create an effective and engaging platform for MOOCs focused on predictive maintenance. The PreMETS project consortium will jointly select the appropriate LMS to develop the most suitable MOOC environment.

Figure 3: Proposed framework for LMS deployment for predictive maintenance

Course description

PreMETS is an ERASMUS+ project aiming at enhancing Predictive Maintenance (PM) practices by addressing the lack of comprehensive PM education in industry, academia, and vocational training. The whole project includes:

- the development of innovative educational toolkits for both PM learners and trainers
- the establishment of a micro-credential certification framework
- the creation of a cross-disciplinary platform integrating various PM resources

This course aims to provide learners with the knowledge and skills to understand and apply the principles and practices of PM. In addition, the goal is set to provide

adequate knowledge and assistance to trainers in order to deliver the material effectively. The following topics are covered:

- A PM training toolkit that integrates VET and higher education EU standards. The PM training toolkit is divided into six different Workforce Needs modules (WN), covering the whole PM realm.
- Provision of a comprehensive toolkit covering an academic EQF 7 level and a professional EQF 4 level, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.
- Establishment of a certification system and skill validation mechanisms, offering recognition and certification for PM skills.

Each trainee can freely select which micro-credential certificates wishes to complete or not. This modular approach follows the EU Digital Certification Framework, which will be described in the following sections and allows the trainee to separately perform the assessment for each WN or TN. Knowledge assessment will use digital assessment formats appropriate to each module, such as multiple-choice questions to assess factual knowledge. PreMETS relies on CFLEX, MICROCREDENTIALS.EU and EPICA project's digital certification approach and this will be embedded in the features of the PreMETS platform (WP4 output) that will allow sufficient customization of the content and assessment to support microcredential awarding. PreMETS' micro-credential modules are linked to the 3 ECTS/ECVET courses developed in WP2 (WN1-WN6 and TN1-TN8).

Trainees who successfully pass the examinations are expected to be able to apply the achieved learning outcomes at a level in line with the level of the qualification diploma. The assessment of trainees involves multiple assessment questions which adequately collect evidence about the capability of a trainee to make judgments to determine whether competency has been achieved. This process confirms that an individual can perform to the standards required in the workplace, as specified in a training package, a vocational education and training (VET) or a higher education accredited course.

In PreMETS, the micro credentials will be structured as MOOCs covering the following features:

- 75 hours of learning; awarded within the context of formal education;
- are explicitly quality assured by external QA;
- are linked to the acquisition of learning outcomes (ECTS level 7 and level 4 courses);
- PreMETS Digital Certificate will be issued.

The PreMETS MOOCs:

- are paving the way for certifications and micro-credentials (observing the GDPR rules) as they are included as a training component for receiving certifications.
- include international keynote speakers and experts in the field of Predictive Maintenance (PM).
- showcase stories/testimonials and best practices of successful application of the present PM strategies and relevant competencies/skills.
- enable virtual participation of any interested target group from the EU and beyond
- include innovative/digital graphical content and pedagogies to boost engagement.

Each module will employ appropriate digital assessment formats, such as multiple-choice questions for factual knowledge.

WN course for students

The examination objectives are designed to align seamlessly with the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance course's learning outcomes, compliant with EQF level 7 (higher education students) and EQF level 4 (VET students), across various modules:

Each WN microcredential module is successfully completed after passing the examination required. The latter involves answering 15 randomised multiple-choice questions from a dedicated pool created for every module. The randomization takes place automatically within the platform, in order to produce a new series of examination questions every time. After the successful completion of all six (6) microcredential modules, the student is awarded the PreMETS Digital Certificate of EQF level 7 or EQF level 4 accordingly.

WN course professional profile

The Higher education (EQF level 7) version of the course presented above is designed for students, teachers, VET trainers, and, even, specialists from a cornucopia of industries (Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics, Transportation etc.), who want to learn more about Predictive Maintenance and how to integrate it in their business environment.

The Vocational Education and Training (EQF level 4) version of the course is tailored for a diverse audience, including students, educators, vocational trainers, and professionals from various sectors such as Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics, and Transportation. It aims to provide comprehensive insights into Predictive Maintenance and its application within different business contexts.

WN course admission requirements

In order to enroll for the Higher Education WN course (EQF 7), the student needs to have completed EQF level 6, or equivalent, in a technical field of study.

In order to enroll for the VET WN course (EQF 4), the student needs to have completed EQF level 3, or equivalent, in a field of study.

Additionally, advanced knowledge of the English language is required for both course versions, for the successful completion of lessons, assignments and examinations.

TN course for trainers

There is also another course available, which runs in parallel and involves micro-credential certificates in Predictive Maintenance targeted to trainers. As with the student version, the trainer qualification is offered at both higher education (EQF 7) and Vocational Education level (EQF 4). The eight (8) modules comprising the trainer course are listed below:

Microcredential TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Microcredential TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Microcredential TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education

Microcredential TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

Microcredential TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources (OERs)

Microcredential TN6: Ethical learner analytics

Microcredential TN7: Microcredential systems and skill validation/certification

Microcredential TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Very similarly to the WN course, successful completion of each TN microcredential module is contingent upon passing a mandatory assessment. This assessment consists of 8 randomly selected multiple-choice questions drawn from a dedicated question pool specific to each module. Again, the platform employs an automated randomisation process, ensuring a unique set of examination questions for each attempt. Upon successful completion of all eight (8) microcredential modules, trainers are awarded the PreMETS Digital Certificate, corresponding to either the EQF level 7 or EQF level 4 framework, based on the chosen course pathway.

TN course professional profile

The Higher education (EQF level 7) version of this course has a target audience of Educators, vocational trainers, industry professionals and specialists with existing knowledge in their field (Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics,

Transportation, etc.) who want to develop expertise in delivering Predictive Maintenance training at higher education level (EQF 7)

The Vocational Education and Training (EQF level 4) version of this course has a target audience of Educators, vocational trainers, and professionals working in various sectors (Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics, Transportation, etc.) who want to gain the knowledge and skills to deliver Predictive Maintenance training at VET level (EQF 4).

TN course admission requirements

Similarly, to the WN course, in order to enroll for the TN course, a professional is required to have previously obtained an EQF level 6 certificate and select either the higher education (EQF 7) or the VET (EQF 4) version of the training program.

From the perspective of language proficiency, both course iterations necessitate an advanced level of English comprehension and production skills for successful completion of instructional modules, assigned tasks, and examinations.

PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate: Examination and Assessment Procedures

Examination Scheduling

Examinations will be available online, on the PreMETS platform after the completion of each module. Adhering to the microcredential ruleset, every module provides its own examination questions and is considered a separate qualification unit. Thus, upon module completion, the user -VET or higher education student or trainer- may initiate an automated examination. After successful results in all microcredential module exams of the selected course, the learner is awarded with the PreMETS Digital Certificate of the respective level achieved.

Specific time limits for different sections of the exam will be defined based on their complexity and the expected time required for completion.

Learning Outcomes Alignment

The examination objectives directly correlate with the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance course's learning outcomes, adhering to the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) Level 7 and Level 4 standards accordingly, across the following modules:

Each module will utilize appropriate digital assessment formats, such as multiple-choice questions for factual knowledge. A combination of formative (training) and summative (assessment) questions will be employed, ensuring both theoretical understanding and practical application are evaluated. The assessment will cater to diverse learning styles and digital proficiency levels. Thus:

- 5 questions from the WP2 assessment questionnaire will be training questions and tasks will be developed to test both theoretical understanding and practical application.
- 15 questions (WP2) for each module that are diverse and inclusive, catering to different learning styles and digital proficiency levels will be used as assessment and certification questions.

The PreMETS micro-credential certifications are designed within the Europass Digital Credentials framework, promoting these EU instruments across Europe. These micro-credentials are linked to the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) Level 7 and Level 4 courses.

This program equips advanced learners with comprehensive knowledge and expertise in predictive maintenance. Learners will gain the ability to design, implement, and optimize predictive maintenance programs, utilize advanced digital tools, and (upon completion of the EQF level 7 course) effectively lead maintenance teams.

In addition to the student course discussed above, there is also an opportunity to enroll to a trainer's course, the completion of which, requires successful examinations in the following TN modules, also offered in both EQF 7 and EQF 4 levels:

TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education

TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources (OERs)

TN6: Ethical learner analytics

TN7: Microcredential systems and skill validation/certification

TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Specifically, each TN module will incorporate digital assessment methods tailored to the learning objectives. These methods will include multiple-choice questions for gauging factual knowledge acquisition. Additionally, a mix of formative (providing feedback for learning) and summative (evaluating final achievement) assessments will be employed to comprehensively assess both theoretical comprehension and the ability to apply knowledge in practical contexts. Furthermore, the assessments will be designed to accommodate diverse learning styles.

- The training component will incorporate 5 questions derived from the WP2 assessment questionnaire. These questions will be designed as practical exercises and tasks, allowing trainees to demonstrate their grasp of theoretical concepts while simultaneously applying their knowledge to real-world scenarios.

- Each module examination will comprise 8 diverse and inclusive questions (also derived from WP2). This approach ensures a fair and comprehensive assessment of learners' knowledge and ensures all learners have an equal opportunity to demonstrate their understanding.

Following the same pattern in the trainer courses, the PreMETS micro-credential certifications adhere to the Europass Digital Credentials framework, thereby actively supporting the dissemination and utilization of these European instruments throughout Europe. These micro-credentials are demonstrably aligned with the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) at Levels 7 and 4.

Examination Objectives

Advanced Maintenance Strategies:

- Explain sophisticated predictive maintenance strategies and their implementation.
- Analyze the cost-effectiveness of predictive maintenance compared to alternative strategies.

Designing Maintenance Programs:

- Develop a comprehensive predictive maintenance program for a complex facility.
- Integrate sustainability and environmentally friendly practices into predictive maintenance planning.

Utilizing Advanced Digital Tools:

- Demonstrate proficiency in using advanced maintenance management software.
- Analyze maintenance data using digital tools and predictive analytics to improve maintenance practices.

Leadership and Team Management:

- Exhibit leadership skills when managing a maintenance team.
- Develop training programs for maintenance personnel to ensure adherence to best practices.

Safety, Compliance, and Risk Management:

- Formulate advanced safety protocols and compliance strategies.
- Conduct risk assessments and implement mitigation strategies within predictive maintenance programs.

Optimization and Continuous Improvement:

- Apply continuous improvement principles to enhance predictive maintenance practices.
- Utilize data-driven approaches to optimize maintenance schedules and minimize downtime.

Assessment Methods

- Case studies and scenario-based exams will evaluate the ability to design and implement maintenance programs.
- Leadership and team management exercises, including role-playing and peer assessments.
- Research projects or dissertations on innovative predictive maintenance techniques.
- Comprehensive oral exams or presentations to demonstrate in-depth understanding and communication skills.

Examination Administration

The PreMETS platform serves as a learning and examination environment. It incorporates a Learning Management System (LMS) and specialized examination software developed under the micro-credential certification framework. This platform facilitates secure test-taking, question randomization, time management, and automated certification or re-examination processes.

Detailed instructions regarding the examination process, rules, and technical requirements will be provided beforehand on the platform.

A clear protocol will be established for trainees to report and resolve issues during examinations. This includes contingency plans for extended time or rescheduling due to technical problems. All information will be publicly available on the platform.

Examination Execution and Processes

Digital submissions will be automatically generated, collected, and secured within the LMS on the PreMETS platform.

Data will be backed up and protected against unauthorized access.

Objective questions will be graded using automated tools, while detailed rubrics will be provided for subjective assessments to ensure consistent and fair grading.

Post-training monitoring recommendations and suggestions for continuous learning will be offered.

Results Compilation and Distribution

Examination results will be analyzed to identify trends, assess areas for improvement, and measure overall achievement.

The LMS analytics tools will facilitate comprehensive performance evaluation.

Successful course completion and mastery of specific skills will be acknowledged through a PreMETS Digital Certificate issued and distributed electronically through the LMS.

Evaluation of Results

Both written and practical examinations (where applicable) will be conducted to award the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate.

Feedback from trainees will be collected to improve the course and teaching methods.

A questionnaire will be administered at the course's conclusion to gather trainee opinions and impressions on the acquired competencies and knowledge, as well as to identify areas for potential improvement.

Eligibility and Passing Requirements

Participants with at least 70% attendance in the training program are eligible for the examination.

To receive the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate, candidates must achieve a minimum score of 70% on the written examination, which consists of multiple-choice questions for each module.

Written Examination

For each module, the written examination will consist of multiple-choice questions, with a minimum of one question per recommended teaching hour.

Each question will have one correct answer among three proposed answers, and candidates will have between 1 and 5 minutes to answer each question, depending on its complexity.

Re-examination Policy

Failure in a single module only requires re-examination of that specific module. However, candidates who fail the same module three times must repeat the relevant video lectures, training materials, and examination.

WN module questions

The following tables present a series of assessment multiple-choice questions designed to evaluate learner comprehension within the WN Predictive Maintenance training program for students. The questions are organized into distinct modules, reflecting the key learning areas covered in the curriculum. Each question is accompanied by a reference to its corresponding learning objectives within the Vocational Education and Training (VET) and Higher Education (HEI) standards frameworks. This allows physical or virtual instructors to readily identify the specific competencies targeted by each assessment item and ensure alignment with established learning outcomes.

The following tables provide a detailed breakdown of the assessment questions. Each table focuses on a specific module and includes four columns:

- Question Number: A unique identifier for each question.
- Question: The actual question formulated to assess learner understanding.
- VET (EQF 4) Standard Compliance: A reference to the relevant competency or learning objective within the VET standards framework.
- Higher Education (EQF 7) Standard Compliance: A reference to the relevant learning outcome or competency within the HEI standards framework.

By utilizing this comprehensive assessment framework, instructors can effectively gauge learner mastery of the Predictive Maintenance subject matter and ensure their training aligns with both VET and HEI standards, accordingly.

Due to the unrestricted public access associated with this document (Public dissemination level), the following tables solely present the question prompts. The answer choices, the designated correct response, and any accompanying feedback associated with incorrect selections are omitted, in order to maintain the integrity of the assessment.

As explained in the learning outcomes alignment section above, the digital platform will randomise 5 questions associated with each module for in-course comprehension assessment. During a microcredential exam of any WN module, 15 related questions will be randomized and presented to the student to answer. After scoring at least 70%, the microcredential certificate will be awarded. Upon successful completion of every microcredential module of the course, the student will receive the PreMETS Digital Certificate of the appropriate EQF level.

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is the role of sensing technologies in Predictive Maintenance?	X	X
2	How does Time Management System (TMS) enhance Predictive Maintenance?		X
3	Which maintenance strategy is characterized by the monitoring of mechanical conditions to prevent failures?	X	X
4	What is one key advantage of Predictive Maintenance over Reactive Maintenance?	X	X
5	What does the concept of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) signify in the context of Predictive Maintenance?	X	X
6	Which of the following best describes the application of sensing technologies in PDM?	X	X
7	What is the primary goal of a Time Management System (TMS) in the context of PDM?		X
8	What distinguishes Predictive Maintenance from Preventive Maintenance?	X	X
9	How do Reporting Models contribute to Predictive Maintenance?		X
10	What does the calculation of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) influence in Predictive Maintenance?	X	X

11	In the context of Industry 4.0, what role do smart sensors play in Predictive Maintenance?	X	X
12	Which of the following is a challenge associated with the implementation of predictive maintenance?		X
13	What is the impact of e-maintenance systems in the realm of PDM?		X
14	How do vibration sensors contribute to fault diagnosis in predictive maintenance?	X	X
15	What is one of the benefits of TPM (Total Productive Maintenance) as a part of maintenance strategies?		X
16	Which type of maintenance is traditionally seen as a cost driver in the production industry?	X	X
17	What does the "bathtub curve" in maintenance methodologies represent?	X	X
18	In Predictive Maintenance, what is the purpose of using machine learning algorithms in the context of RUL?	X	X
19	Which of these is a primary challenge in the integration of sensors for Predictive Maintenance within Industry 4.0?		X
20	What is the main advantage of using ultrasonic sensors in Predictive Maintenance?	X	X
21	How do decentralized smart industry systems contribute to Predictive Maintenance in Industry 4.0?		X
22	What is a key feature of e-maintenance systems in the context of Industry 4.0?		X
23	What is the impact of the Digital Twin concept on the development of a Time Management System (TMS) for Predictive Maintenance?		X
24	Why is continuous validation important in Predictive Maintenance systems?	X	X
25	What is the primary benefit of incorporating Machine Learning (ML) into Predictive Maintenance systems?	X	X

26	What are the key components of an effective reporting model for construction project management?		X
27	How can reporting models be adapted to ensure compliance with evolving safety regulations in the construction industry?		X
28	What are the most common non-destructive testing (NDT) methods used for structural assessment in construction?	X	X
29	How has the integration of BIM (Building Information Modeling) technology impacted structural assessment methods?		X
30	What role do forecasting systems play in the planning and execution of large-scale transportation projects?		X
31	Can you explain how remote infrastructure management systems contribute to the efficiency of transport logistics?		X
32	What are the challenges faced in implementing remote infrastructure management systems in existing transportation networks?		X
33	What are the benefits and drawbacks of using AI-based predictive maintenance in the construction and transport industries?	X	X
34	How has the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the need for remote infrastructure management solutions in construction and transport sectors?		X

Module WN2: Digital skills for PM

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	Collection of temperature and pressure data categorizes as	X	X
2	Collection of data about physical location categorizes as		X

3	Sensor readings stored in the database is	X	X
4	XML documents are		X
5	Video recordings are	X	X
6	Data cleaning in the data transformation process involves	X	X
7	Which of the following best defines a digital twin?		X
8	How are digital twins used in industrial manufacturing enterprises?	X	X
9	Benefits of virtual reality (VR) in maintenance include:		X
10	How are drones, robotics, and exoskeleton technology primarily utilized in maintenance tasks?	X	X
11	IoT devices use sensor to	X	X
12	IoT devices use actuators to		X
13	Predictive maintenance uses		X
14	In the context of predictive maintenance, what technology is utilized to capture conditions of machines and equipment and enable intelligent actions through machine learning?		X
15	What is the primary goal of Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM)?	X	X
16	What role does Predictive Analytics play in Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM)?		X
17	How does Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) differ from Predictive Maintenance (PM)?	X	X
18	What is a key element in Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) that involves the establishment of a normal operating condition for each piece of equipment?		X
19	What is the primary purpose of Vibration Monitoring in predictive maintenance?	X	X
20	Which method in Visual Inspection involves using ultraviolet (UV) light to reveal fluorescent indications of issues such as leaks or contamination?	X	X

21	What is a limitation of ultrasonics in the context of predictive maintenance, as mentioned in the text?		X
22	Which of the following is a characteristic of Knowledge-Based Models in fault prediction for predictive maintenance?		X
23	What does the Data-Based Models approach in fault prediction primarily use to predict failures in the current state?	X	X
24	What is the primary function of Rule-Based Systems in predictive maintenance?	X	X
25	How does Knowledge Representation contribute to decision-making in predictive maintenance?		X
26	What is the primary objective of supervised learning in the context of machine learning?		X
27	What is the biggest challenge when implementing Machine Learning (ML) in Predictive Maintenance (PM) applications?	X	X
28	What is the purpose of Survival Models in the context of predictive maintenance?		X
29	What role does anomaly detection play in predictive maintenance, and what are the challenges associated with evaluating anomaly detection models?	X	X
30	What are some commonly used models for predicting remaining useful lifetime (RUL), and what metrics are used to evaluate the performance of regression models in predictive maintenance?		X
31	Predictive maintenance systems often operate in which type of networks?		X
32	Incorporating cybersecurity into predictive maintenance reaches what overall goal?		X
33	Which task is imperative in order to comply with security measures?	X	X
34	Which major cybersecurity tasks are included to be in line with regulatory compliances?	X	X

35	Regulatory compliance can be achieved in what manner?	X	X
36	What unique information does each blockchain transaction hold?		X
37	A block within the blockchain can be viewed as?		X
38	In terms of node structure, a blockchain can be viewed as?	X	X
39	Technology-wise, a blockchain is?		X
40	What are smart contracts?	X	X
41	Trello is a visual project management software that uses what kind of tools?	X	X
42	Which software is a computerized maintenance system?		X
43	Which software is an enterprise level asset management solution?		X

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What does the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework help investors assess?	X	X
2	What is the primary focus of ESG reporting?	X	X
3	What is the purpose of ESG compliance?	X	X
4	What do ESG metrics assess?	X	X
5	What does an ESG rating or score serve as?	X	X
6	What is greenwashing in the context of ESG reporting?	X	X
7	What is suggested as a top priority in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reports due to the urgency of climate change?	X	X
8	How can customers' willingness to pay for products with reduced GHG emissions be inferred?		X
9	What does Scope 2 of the Greenhouse Gas Protocol involve?	X	X

10	What poses the greatest challenge in terms of reliable and comparable measurement across different companies and over time?	X	X
11	What innovative method was introduced in a study by Razali et al. in 2015 to address the environmental challenge posed by the membrane fabrication process?	X	X
12	What is suggested as a potential solution for manufacturing companies grappling with measurement challenges in their GHG reporting frameworks?	X	X
13	What is the main objective of evaluating products, services, processes, and larger-scale endeavors across various environmental indicators?	X	X
14	What is the fundamental component of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)?	X	X
15	What does the Tiered hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) method involve?	X	X
16	How does the Path Exchange (PXC) hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) method work?	X	X
17	What is one of the factors that impedes the widespread adoption of hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods?	X	X
18	Why is it recommended to adopt a consistent framework for classifying and defining hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods?		X
19	What is a significant challenge confronting present-day industries, considering the depletion of non-renewable resources and increasing environmental awareness?	X	X
20	What are additional incentives for industries to transition to environmentally friendly manufacturing solutions, beyond regulatory standards?	X	X
21	What is an example of an environment-oriented software tool mentioned in the text?	X	X

22	What role do evaluation and surveillance of energy and resource efficiency play in sustainable manufacturing practices?	X	X
23	What is the purpose of Resources Value Mapping mentioned in the text?	X	X
24	According to the text, how can energy efficiency be enhanced without compromising productivity in manufacturing?	X	X
25	What distinguishes technologies associated with renewable energy in terms of carbon emissions?	X	X
26	How are clean energy sources defined in the text?	X	X
27	What term is used to describe less polluting forms of energy, recognizing that no energy source is completely pristine?	X	X
28	What role did wind, solar, hydrothermal, hydrogen, and biomass-based energy systems play during the sudden onset of COVID-19?	X	X
29	What is the term used to describe the energy flexibility control of manufacturing systems in the context of variable renewable energy (VRE)?	X	X
30	What is a primary choice for renewable energy in manufacturing due to its versatility and substitution potential?	X	X

Module WN4: Resilience competences for PM

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What does adaptability entail in the context of predictive maintenance?	X	X
2	Which skill is crucial for promptly diagnosing issues within transportation equipment or infrastructure?	X	X
3	What is the primary benefit of maintaining composure and focus under	X	X

	high-pressure situations in maintenance tasks?		
4	Which skill involves evaluating potential risks associated with equipment failure or infrastructure issues?	X	X
5	What does resourcefulness entail in maintenance operations?	X	X
6	Which skill involves a meticulous approach to inspections and identifying even minor abnormalities?	X	X
7	What is essential for adhering to maintenance schedules and ensuring timely completion of tasks?	X	X
8	Which skill involves clear and concise communication with all stakeholders in the maintenance process?	X	X
9	What is crucial for staying updated with the latest technological advancements and industry best practices in maintenance?	X	X
10	Which skill involves adjusting to changing priorities or unexpected situations in maintenance tasks?	X	X
11	Which platform is known for its risk evaluation capabilities, particularly using the bowtie method?		X
12	What is essential for effective risk management in maintenance operations?		X
13	Which tool is specifically designed for process hazard analysis, including Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP)?		X
14	What is crucial for developing effective mitigation strategies in maintenance operations?	X	X
15	What is a critical aspect of monitoring and reviewing mitigation strategies in maintenance operations?		X
16	What is a crucial aspect of developing mitigation strategies for high-priority risks?		X
17	In the context of staff training, what does "continuous learning" refer to?	X	X

18	What is the primary objective of stakeholder involvement in risk assessment?		X
19	What is a key benefit of using Microsoft Teams for stakeholder involvement?		X
20	How does structured documentation contribute to effective risk assessment?		X
21	What is the purpose of version control in documentation?		X
22	What is a key advantage of utilizing IoT devices for real-time monitoring in maintenance operations?		X
23	How does continuous training contribute to resilience in maintenance operations?	X	X
24	What is the primary purpose of regular review and improvement in maintenance processes?	X	X
25	How does effective documentation support resilience in maintenance operations?	X	X
26	What aspect of maintenance does Dude Solutions MaintenanceEdge focus on?		X
27	What emerging technology is expected to play an increasingly important role in predictive maintenance?		X
28	Which strategy is recommended for organizations to meet future needs in predictive maintenance?	X	X
29	What will be a priority in predictive maintenance, requiring competence in environmentally friendly technologies?		X
30	Which technology will connect multiple devices and systems, generating massive amounts of data for predictive maintenance?		X

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	When did the concept of Predictive Maintenance emerge?	X	X

2	What distinguishes predictive maintenance from traditional maintenance approaches?	X	X
3	What is one major benefit of predictive maintenance over traditional maintenance?	X	X
4	What is a significant challenge in adopting predictive maintenance?	X	X
5	How does AI contribute to predictive maintenance?	X	X
6	What role does the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) play in predictive maintenance?	X	X
7	In predictive maintenance, what does machine learning primarily focus on?	X	X
8	What is an entrepreneurial mindset in the context of predictive maintenance?	X	X
9	What is adaptive thinking important for in predictive maintenance?		X
10	Which marketing approach is crucial for predictive maintenance services?		X
11	What is a key element of branding in predictive maintenance?		X
12	What is a primary target in marketing predictive maintenance solutions?		X
13	How does predictive maintenance contribute to sustainability?	X	X
14	What is a critical skill for market analysis in predictive maintenance?		X
15	What does SWOT analysis in predictive maintenance involve?		X
16	What is a benefit of leveraging IoT and data science in predictive maintenance?	X	X
17	What is an advantage of implementing predictive maintenance for businesses?		X
18	What is the main barrier of implementing predictive maintenance in companies?		X
19	TBM or time-based maintenance is called	X	X
20	What is the difference between preventive and predictive maintenance?	X	X
21	How many elements did W.Tiddens, T. Tinga and J. Braaksma propose to		X

	support effective maintenance techniques (MT)-based decision-making?		
22	What are the elements proposed by W.Tiddens, T. Tinga and J. Braaksma to support effective maintenance techniques (MT)-based decision-making?		X
23	The PReMMa model can help companies to:		X
24	Predictive Maintenance:	X	X
25	A creativity technique to create a free and open environment that encourages everyone's participation and makes it possible for all team members to share their knowledge and creativity is:		X
26	Contemporary tools and technologies:		X
27	A tool that can automate repetitive tasks, allowing for more innovative changes with the elimination of routine work is:	X	X
28	Predictive maintenance based on continuous and ongoing monitoring of machines:	X	X
29	There are benefits to implementing predictive maintenance systems:	X	X
30	The most effective approach to maintenance in pneumatics would be to use a strategy:	X	X
31	The benefits of introducing predictive maintenance include:	X	X
32	According to Deloitte, companies that have invested in predictive maintenance have seen cost reductions of:		X
33	In the field of marketing, comprehensive technology support provides:		X

Module WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is a key aspect of online learning? Limited availability of learning materials	X	X
2	What is a characteristic feature of asynchronous online learning?	X	X

3	Which of the following is an example of asynchronous learning in the corporate sector?	X	X
4	What is one advantage of recorded sessions in asynchronous learning environments?		X
5	What is a key characteristic of Synchronous Online Learning (SOL)?	X	X
6	What is a key characteristic of a Personal Learning Environment (PLE) in the context of predictive maintenance?	X	X
7	Which component of a PLE for predictive maintenance provides opportunities for knowledge exchange, mentorship, and collaboration with peers and experts?	X	X
8	What is the VARK model primarily used for?	X	X
9	Which learning preference involves learning best through listening?	X	X
10	What does the VARK model suggest for visual learners to enhance their learning experience?		X
11	What is predictive maintenance (PdM) in engineering primarily focused on?		X
12	How might a professional seminar on predictive maintenance engage auditory learners?	X	X
13	Which of the following visual learning strategies involves the use of detailed illustrations to depict scientific phenomena or engineering mechanisms?		X
14	What type of learner benefits from engaging in verbal interactions and listening to explanations to grasp complex subjects?		X
15	How can read/write learners reinforce their understanding and retention of study materials?	X	X
16	Which learning style involves hands-on experiences and direct engagement with the material world?	X	X

17	Which strategy can help kinesthetic learners maintain focus and absorb information?	X	X
18	What is the purpose of the Pedagogical Framework?		X
19	What is the primary emphasis of the Constructivist Learning Theory?		X
20	According to Bada and Olusegun, what is the role of teachers in a constructivist learning environment?		X
21	What is the primary focus of Technology-Enhanced Learning (TEL)?	X	X
22	What is the primary characteristic of the Flipped Classroom Model?	X	X
23	What is a key characteristic of Problem-Based Learning (PBL)?	X	X
24	What distinguishes Competency-Based Education (CBE) from traditional time-based learning?	X	X
25	What is a key benefit of implementing collaborative learning in engineering education, according to the research by Ralston, Tretter, and Brown (2017)?		X
26	Which of the following best describes the essence of experiential learning?	X	X
27	Which educational approach involves the use of Six Thinking Hats, a method introduced by Edward de Bono in 1985, to guide users in adopting different perspectives towards problem-solving and creative thinking?		X
28	Which learning strategy allows learners to actively engage with new material by organizing what they already know, what they want to know, and what they have learned?		X
29	Which model is used as a tool to develop self-awareness and mutual understanding by dividing information into four areas, including the open or free area, facade or hidden area, blind spot, and unknown area?		X

30	Which method involves individuals evaluating the performance, contributions, or skills of their peers within a group or team, offering a more holistic assessment and incorporating insights from various perspectives?	X	X
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TN module questions

In the question lists shown below lies the core of the assessment strategy for the TN Predictive Maintenance training program for trainers, catering to both Vocational Education and Training (VET) and Higher Education (HEI) contexts. The assessment aims to evaluate trainee comprehension of key learning areas covered in the program curriculum.

The following tables provide a detailed breakdown of the assessment questions categorized by TN modules. Each table includes four key elements:

- Question Number: A unique identifier assigned to each question.
- Question: The specific question designed to assess learner understanding of the subject matter.
- VET (EQF 4) Standard Compliance: Reference to the specific competency or learning objective within the VET framework targeted by the question.
- Higher Education (EQF 7) Standard Compliance: Reference to the relevant learning outcome or competency addressed by the question within the HEI framework.

This alignment ensures the assessment directly measures knowledge and skills aligned with established learning standards for both VET and HEI programs.

Due to the public availability of this document, the answer choices, designated correct responses, and any feedback associated with incorrect selections are intentionally omitted. This approach safeguards the integrity of the assessment and prevents potential exposure to students.

As described in the learning outcomes alignment section above, the digital platform will randomly select 5 questions per module for in-course assessment purposes.

Microcredential exams for each TN module will present students with a randomized set of 8 related questions. Students must achieve a score of at least

70% to receive a microcredential certificate. Upon successful completion of all microcredential modules in the course, students will be awarded the PreMETS Digital Certificate at the appropriate EQF level.

Module TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is emphasized as a crucial factor influencing student learning?	X	X
2	According to Clark et al. (2016), what is the impact of goal setting on student performance?	X	X
3	How can educators enhance learning outcomes using technology?	X	X
4	What is a key characteristic of constructivist learning environments, as noted by Jonassen (1994)?		X
5	According to Siemens (2005), what is a critical principle of connectivism?		X
6	How does connectivism differ from traditional views of learning, according to Anderson and Dron (2011)?		X
7	What is emphasizing regarding 21st-century skills?	X	X
8	According to the Foundation for Young Australians (2017), why are transferable skills important for young people?		X
9	What is emphasized as crucial for the effectiveness of technology in learning?	X	X
10	What is the primary focus of active learning?	X	X
11	What are some characteristics of active learning strategies?		X

12	How does the constructivist learning theory contribute to active learning, according to Hativa (2000)?		X
13	What does Mickelson et al. (2009) suggest about the role of students during active learning based on constructivist theory?	X	X
14	What is the primary goal of learner empowerment?	X	X
15	According to Kirk et al. (2016), what benefits are associated with highly empowered students?	X	X
16	What are the four dimensions of empowerment, according to Thomas and Velthos as cited in Frymier and Houser (1996)?	X	X
17	How can instructors improve students' involvement and higher-order thinking tasks?		X
18	What is the main purpose of formative assessment in the context of active learning?	X	X
19	How does peer assessment contribute to the empowerment of learners in the teaching and learning process?	X	X
20	What are the characteristics of effective feedback, according to Hattie and Timperley (2007)?		X
21	How could trainers achieve ongoing collaboration in an online and/or asynchronous mode, according to Yoon et al. (2020)?	X	X

Module TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is dropout primarily defined as?	X	X
2	Which of the following terms is synonymous with dropout?	X	X
3	What does the term "retention" mean in the context of online education?	X	X
4	Why are dropout rates in higher education a major concern?		X
5	Which challenge is NOT mentioned for online learners?	X	X
6	What significantly affects the persistence of online learners?	X	X
7	What is a student-focused definition of persistence?	X	X
8	How do dropout rates impact universities?		X
9	For students, what does dropping out entail?	X	X
10	Which is NOT a persistence factor related to online learners?	X	X
11	Which factor influences persistence related to online courses and course providers?	X	X
12	What role do online instructors play in reducing dropout rates?	X	X
13	How can dropout rates in online courses be reduced?	X	X
14	What is a proactive measure to address dropout rates?	X	X
15	What is important in the initial session of a course to set student expectations?	X	X

16	The use of learning analytics is suggested for:	X	X
17	Providing proactive academic advisory is aimed at:	X	X
18	Continuous quality assurance involves:	X	X
19	What is NOT a suggested action to reduce dropout rates in online courses?	X	X
20	Dropout rates can be mitigated by:	X	X

Module TN3: Inclusion of groups at risk and personalized education

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is a major limitation of traditional education models?	X	X
2	What gap is highlighted in traditional education regarding predictive maintenance?		X
3	Who are considered vulnerable in educational settings?	X	X
4	What challenge do at-risk groups face in predictive maintenance education?	X	X
5	What is a key advantage of fostering inclusion in education?	X	X
6	How does inclusion affect student success in predictive maintenance education?	X	X
7	What defines personalized education?	X	X
8	What is crucial for curriculum design in personalized education?		X
9	What role does technology play in personalized learning?	X	X

10	Which tool is essential for online delivery in education?	X	X
11	What does adaptive learning leverage for personalized education?	X	X
12	How does predictive maintenance data enhance education?	X	X
13	What is a strategy for implementing personalized education?		X
14	What recommendation is given for educators in predictive maintenance?		X
15	What is essential for engaging students in predictive maintenance education?		X
16	How can educators overcome the one-size-fits-all model?		X
17	What barrier does inclusive education aim to break down?		X
18	What is a benefit of using technology in predictive maintenance education?	X	X
19	Why is real-world relevance important in personalized education?	X	X
20	What outcome does fostering diversity and inclusion in education aim for?	X	X

Module TN4: Strategies for generating brain plasticity and learning connections

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	The AGES model, proposed by the Associate Professor of Psychology at New York University Lila Davachi, stands for:		X
2	According to the AGES model, is it possible to multi-task while learning something new?		X

3	Adults build on prior learning and take as much responsibility as they want for their ongoing learning (Illeris, 2010). As a result, self-directed learning methods are highly effective in adults.'	X	X
4	Including games in learning programs with relevant context increases learning outcomes.	X	X
5	When 'spacing' learning content, it is important to:	X	X
6	Of the factors that influence student learning, which one of the most potent?	X	X
7	People who are actively engaged, no matter the situation, are more productive.	X	X
8	Technology can aid motivation and engagement only when:	X	X
9	According to Sheninger and Murray, 2017, empowerment is improved through:		X
10	A pedagogical strategy that allows students to work collaboratively on meaningful tasks at their own level and pace (Prensky, 2001) through activities such as task-based learning is called:		X
11	Springer et al. (1999) investigated task-based learning further and found that the best results, in terms of positive effect size, were to be obtained through:		X
12	Neuroplasticity is:		X
13	Cortisol, released during stress, depresses synaptic plasticity.		X
14	Dopamine and ACh, released during states of motivation and attention, do NOT boost synaptic plasticity.		X
15	Behavioral learning and the formation of memories is associated with:	X	X

16	How many hours have the researchers estimated for young people being engaged on some form of Internet-connected device?	X	X
17	A connectivism learning theory:		X
18	As noted by Jonassen, 1994, there are how many main characteristics of constructivist learning environments?	X	X
19	Who is considered as the father of connectivist learning theory?	X	X
20	SMART Objectives stands for:	X	X

Module TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources (OERs)

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is the core principle behind Open Educational Resources?	X	X
2	When did the academic uptake and development of OERs take place?		X
3	How did the Covid-19 pandemic impact the uptake of Open Educational Resources?		X
4	Which organization coined the term "Open Educational Resources" during a 2002 conference?		X
5	According to the OECD, what does OER include, besides learning content?	X	X
6	What is the significance of the Cape Town Open Education Declaration, as mentioned in the text?		X
7	According to David Wiley, what are the 5R activities/permissions associated with OERs?	X	X

8	Why are materials accessed through library subscriptions not considered OERs?		X
9	What is one of the advantages of OERs for educational institutions based on the altruistic argument?		X
10	How do OERs contribute to financial savings for students and parents?	X	X
11	What is one challenge associated with OERs related to Quality Assurance?		X
12	How can trainers effectively integrate OERs into their teaching, according to the recommendations?	X	X
13	What should trainers emphasize when using OERs to avoid common pitfalls?	X	X
14	What is the potential drawback of the proliferation of OER initiatives in recent years, according to the text?		X
15	What future trend is associated with the digitization of media in the development of OERs?		X
16	What is one advantage of OERs for individual involvement highlighted in the text?		X
17	What is recommended to trainers to ensure the cultural relevance of OER materials?	X	X
18	What is a potential challenge associated with the establishment of central platforms for OERs?		X
19	According to the text, what should trainers emphasize when using OERs to avoid common pitfalls?	X	X
20	What is the primary driver in the implementation of OERs related to copyright issues, as mentioned in the text?		X

Module TN6: Ethical learner analytics

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What does ethical learner analytics entail in the context of preventive maintenance?		X
2	Which is the least significant benefit of ethical learning analytics could offer?	X	X
3	Which cutting-edge technology assists in launching an effective learning system in predictive maintenance?	X	X
4	Based on what you know/learned, what is the impact of using emerging technologies such as AI & Machine Learning in predictive maintenance?	X	X
5	In what type of data does the advanced learning systems rely on?	X	X
6	What is emphasized as crucial for the effectiveness of technology in learning?		X
7	Why is it important to prioritize ethical considerations in the application of learner analytics?		X
8	How can data privacy and security be maintained when collecting and analyzing learner data for preventive maintenance purposes?		X
9	What steps can organizations take to ensure transparency in the use of learner analytics for preventive maintenance?		X
10	Discuss the potential risks of using learner analytics in preventive maintenance without proper ethical guidelines.		X

11	How can bias be mitigated in the development and implementation of learner analytics models for preventive maintenance?		X
12	What role does informed consent play in ethical learner analytics practices for preventive maintenance?	X	X
13	Explain the concept of fairness and equity in the context of using learner analytics for preventive maintenance decision-making.		X
14	How can organizations ensure accountability and governance in the use of learner analytics for preventive maintenance?		X
15	What measures can be taken to prevent the misuse of learner data?	X	X
16	How can organizations promote inclusivity and diversity in the development and application of learner analytics?		X
17	Explain the concept of algorithmic transparency and its importance in ethical learner analytics for preventive maintenance.	X	X
18	What strategies can be employed to ensure continuous reflection and improvement of ethical learner analytics practices in preventive maintenance?		X
19	How can organizations foster a culture of ethical awareness and responsibility among stakeholders involved in preventive maintenance analytics?	X	X
20	What role does data stewardship play in ensuring ethical learner analytics practices in preventive maintenance?		X
21	Reflect on a real-world scenario where ethical considerations were paramount in the application of learner analytics for preventive maintenance, and discuss the lessons learned.		X

Module TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What is the primary aim of the European recommendation on micro-credentials?	X	X
2	What role do micro-credentials play in individuals' learning pathways?	X	X
3	What key challenge does the booklet address regarding micro-credentials in Europe?		X
4	How do micro-credentials contribute to addressing skill gaps?	X	X
5	European businesses and employers grapple with:		X
6	What is the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan's target regarding adult training participation?		X
7	How can micro-credentials be designed and issued?	X	X
8	What is the primary obstacle to the realization of the full potential of micro-credentials?		X
9	How do micro-credentials relate to the European Green Deal?	X	X
10	What is the overarching goal of the European Skills Agenda?	X	X
11	How does the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) contribute to the recognition of micro-credentials?	X	X
12	What role do micro-credentials play in supporting the goals of the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027?		X
13	What is the main focus on the validation of non-formal and informal learning?		X

14	What is the purpose of Europass?		X
15	How does the content suggest micro-credentials can contribute to a socially fair recovery?	X	X
16	What is a key characteristic of micro-credentials?	X	X
17	What are the three main characteristics of micro-credentials?	X	X
18	Which of the following is NOT listed as a mandatory element for describing micro-credentials?	X	X
19	What is an example of an optional element for describing micro-credentials?	X	X
20	How many principles describe micro-credentials?	X	X

Module TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Question number	Question	VET (EQF 4)	HEI (EQF 7)
1	What does CRAAP test serve for?	X	X
2	What does CRAAP acronym stand for?	X	X
3	Currency in CRAAP test evaluates:	X	X
4	OER stands for:		X
5	What principle do OER need to meet?	X	X
6	What is the 5r's principle?	X	X
7	Why is collaboration considered one of the biggest advantages of OER?		X
8	What are some potential drawbacks to OER?	X	X
9	What is the best way to identify learning objectives and outcomes when learning via OER?		X

10	What educational tools can you use to repurpose existing materials?		X
11	What are the advantages of repurposing existing materials?		X
12	Why do discussion forums have learning potential?		X
13	What is the future of OER?		X
14	Which stakeholders need to be taken into account when reusing OER?		X
15	In order to facilitate taking using discussion forums as learning source, it is essential to:	X	X
16	What criteria are recommended for evaluating existing resources and materials before repurposing them?		X
17	Why is it important to personalize and customize existing resources and materials during repurposing?		X
18	What is one of the main challenges associated with extracting useful information from discussion forums?		X
19	What is suggested as a solution for organizing information from discussion forums into a usable format?		X
20	What is the aim of the booklet on (Re)use of Existing Infrastructures and Learning Resources?	X	X

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Appendix I: EQF Framework

EQF Level	Knowledge	Skills	Responsibility and Autonomy
	<i>In the context of EQF, knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual</i>	<i>In the context of EQF, skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)</i>	<i>In the context of the EQF responsibility and autonomy is described as the ability of the learner to apply knowledge and skills autonomously and with responsibility</i>
8	Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and at the interface between fields	The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, required to solve critical problems in research and/or innovation and to extend and redefine existing knowledge or professional practice	Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity and sustained commitment to the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts including research
7	Highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in a field of work or study, as the basis for original thinking and/or research Critical awareness of knowledge issues in a field and at the interface between different fields	Specialised problem-solving skills required in research and/or innovation in order to develop new knowledge and procedures and to integrate knowledge from different fields	Manage and transform work or study contexts that are complex, unpredictable and require new strategic approaches; take responsibility for contributing to professional knowledge and practice and/or for reviewing the strategic performance of teams
6	Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles	Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work or study	Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, taking responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts; take responsibility for managing professional development of individuals and groups
5	Comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge within a field of work or study and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge	A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems	Exercise management and supervision in contexts of work or study activities where there is unpredictable change; review and develop performance of self and others
4	Factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts within a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study	Exercise self-management within the guidelines of work or study contexts that are usually predictable, but are subject to change; supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities
3	Knowledge of facts, principles, processes and general concepts, in a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials and information	Take responsibility for completion of tasks in work or study; adapt own behaviour to circumstances in solving problems
2	Basic factual knowledge of a field of work or study	Basic cognitive and practical skills required to use relevant information in order to carry out tasks and to solve routine problems using simple rules and tools	Work or study under supervision with some autonomy
1	Basic general knowledge	Basic skills required to carry out simple tasks	Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context

Description of the eight EQF levels - <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-efq-levels>

Source: <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-efq-levels>

Appendix II: D3.1 - PreMETS certification framework language translations

D3.1 - PreMETS certification framework has been translated in Romanian, Greek, Italian, German, Dutch and Serbian. A link to these translated documents can be found below.

D3.1 - PreMETS certification framework (Language translations)

Link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1WPX2tq6JSF4LYn0Gc4zkDZEBVOoXVRmZ?usp=sharing>

PreMETS

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